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**ADVANTAGES OF MOBILE APPPOSITIONS IN IMPROVING THE
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Annotation: The article discusses the vantages of the mobile appositions model in improving the educational process in higher education, modern achievements of mobile technologies in the education system, and analysis of existing scientific publications on the use of software in the educational process, problems and relevance of the idea.

Key words: higher education institutions, education system, mobile appositions, mobile technologies, virtual environment, improving the efficiency of the educational process, mobile apposition model.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются преимущества модели мобильных приложений в совершенствовании образовательного процесса в высшей школе, современные достижения мобильных технологий в системе образования, анализ существующих научных публикаций по использованию программного обеспечения в образовательном процессе, проблемы и актуальность идеи.

Ключевые слова: высшие учебные заведения, система образования, мобильные приложения, мобильные технологии, виртуальная среда, повышение эффективности образовательного процесса, модель мобильного приложения.

Introduction.

It is no coincidence that the 21st century is called the century of information technology all over the world. The sharp increase in the use of information technology has led to the introduction of new approaches to the education system, the terms mobile technologies, mobile applications, mobile education. This is an important software tool in improving the efficiency of the educational process in higher education institutions. Educational software is improving and new technologies such as mobile technologies are being developed. Mobile technology is a prototype of information technology devices, which are much cheaper in quality and more efficient. Such mobile technologies are cheaper than tablets, laptops and computers, and connecting to the Internet is much more convenient and easier. Mobile applications are the basis of learning using mobile technologies. Mobile applications are useful for improving the learning process in higher education institutions. It also serves as an aid to students. At the same

time, one of the urgent tasks is to improve the educational process in educational institutions based on mobile applications.

Literature analysis and methodology.

An analysis of existing scientific publications on the use of mobile applications in the educational process shows that the issue of using mobile applications in the educational process is given great attention all over the world. J. Traxler states: "Mobile learning is changing the entire learning process. Training will be adequate and timely individualized." D. Kelly Mobile education is not a process of transferring educational materials to a small screen and using mobile devices, but a way to introduce innovative forms of education: the development of materials for innovative mobile applications with educational microblogs, news feeds, course broadcasts, etc. process. The use of mobile applications in the educational process provides the following benefits:

1. The possibility of self-study outside the educational process;
2. Analysis of modern information technologies;
3. Development of mobile applications and online services;
4. The ability for students to choose useful mobile applications;
5. Improving the educational process in higher education institutions based on mobile applications;
6. Encouraging nature of the educational process;
7. unified control over the level of knowledge of students;
8. Accelerate the exchange of information between participants in the learning process;
9. Flexibility of mobile applications in an individual approach, taking into account the individual psychological and physiological characteristics of students (Individual approach).

The introduction of mobile applications in the educational process in higher education institutions increases the efficiency of mastering and memorizing the course by students. The interest of students in the performance of tasks, the exchange of information, the increase in discussions will lead to the revival of the audience, which will increase the effectiveness of learning. A student may have a different approach to the process of using mobile applications when designing lessons in a traditional form of education. For example, A. Amirov, A. Ashimbekova, A. Temirova divided the use of mobile devices in the learning process into the following groups:

1. Multimedia training - to demonstrate web resources (animations, audio files, videos, graphics, maps and images);

2. Provide quick access to educational sites, resources, reference books, dictionaries;

3. Provide communication during the learning process (SMS messages, Twitter, Telegram, FaceBook, webinars, etc.).

Mobile education is an opportunity for continuous independent learning and universal exchange of information. In addition, distance education systems provide equal opportunities for everyone, regardless of social status, people (students, schoolchildren, ordinary people, military personnel, the unemployed, etc.) to independently exchange information at any time.

Such an education system will make it possible to fully realize the educational needs of every citizen of our country, which is a constitutional right. Principles of using mobile applications in educational institutions;

Mobile applications are the principle of transition to a new level of e-learning using information technology, mobile technology and the Internet.

- students can interact and communicate with the teacher;
- Classrooms are easier to accommodate multiple mobile devices than desktop computers;
- there is an opportunity to share information and work together; students and teachers will be able to send, edit, reload and send texts to special groups wirelessly.
- new technical means, mobile applications, mobile phones, gadgets will further increase students' interest in learning;
- Mobile learning makes learning more personal. Students will have the opportunity to choose the content of training based on their interests. Mobile applications in the learning process is a space of great opportunities for students;
- The use of mobile applications increases the flexibility of students' activities, the ability to quickly search for information necessary for their work;
- The main feature of mobile applications is the ability to self-learn and quickly obtain information upon request.

The use of a blended method that incorporates various software tools to make learning effective and fun is the latest trend in education. Blended learning combines different types of learning and creates an interactive learning environment based on this method. Improving the educational process in higher education institutions based on mobile applications will increase the effectiveness of learning.

Results.

We know that today mobile phones have entered almost all spheres of human life. If earlier it was enough to have books, notebooks, pens, paper and mind, today, in the conditions of fierce competition of modern society, students need more modern information technologies. Today it has become clear that tablets, innovative technologies, computer programs have a strong influence on the approach to education, on the education system as a whole.

Conclusion.

In short, mobile applications allow data to be used in a way that is deliberately consistent (compatible) with each other. This allows you to present knowledge in various forms using modern teaching methods. At the same time, learning through mobile applications not only master's educational materials, but also increases the desire of poorly mastered students to acquire new knowledge. Learning using mobile applications has become the basis for increasing the activity of students, the effectiveness of their learning.

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